

PHTHALATES: AN ENDOCRINE DISRUPTING COSMETIC EXCIPIENT

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ABSTRACT

Phthalates are used as an excipient in every other cosmetic product, also phthalates are found in products which encounter plastic e.g. plastic packing, plastic box, phthalates are unavoidable in current world. Despite the short half-life continuous exposure to the phthalates will lead to endocrine disruption and impair functioning of organs, have negative impact on pregnancy, child growth, many countries have lead several restrictions on various types of phthalates. This article aims to summarise the toxic effect of phthalates and suggest ways to decrease exposure to phthalates.

KEYWORDS: Phthalates, Endocrine disruptors, Cosmetic excipients, Plasticizers, Toxicity, Reproductive toxicity, Environmental exposure, Human health, DEHP, Consumer products, Hormonal disruption, Phthalate exposure, Plastic pollution, Cosmetic safety, Semi-volatile organic compounds.

INTRODUCTION

Plastic has its benefits to the society since it was invented in 1907, but it also has many negative effects on the environment and human health, which has become a big global problem. People are constantly exposed to plastics via contaminated food, packaging leachate (e.g., water bottle and medical devices), atmospheric fallout and urban dust containing microplastics, personal care products (Phthalate Plasticizers) (e.g., cosmetic packaging), and

synthetic clothing.^[1,2] The extended interaction with plastic materials would result in the emission of many hazardous compounds. The most alarming thing is the presence of phthalates in cosmetics and other plastic related products, bisphenol A, and polychlorinated biphenyls. They are classified as endocrine disruptors due to their interference with hormones.^[3,4]

1. Exposure

Plastic waste is receiving considerable attention from regulatory authorities. Globally, the consumption of plastic includes 3 million tons of phthalates every year. The reason why there is extensive exposure of phthalates with humans is because of these substances are highly abundant within the natural environment. For instance, China experienced over three times growth in its plastic consumption between 2003 and 2011, with 50 million tons of the raw plastics being produced in that period.^[5] Certain dairy products, fishes, sea foods, and oils contain high amounts of phthalates. People who are residing near factories producing phthalates tend to be exposed to phthalates either through dermal exposure or by breathing in polluted air.^[6] Absorption through skin takes place due to the everyday usage of consumer goods that contain phthalates in their packaging materials. Babies are also exposed to phthalates because of feeding on breast milk, which contains Di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate and Diisononyl phthalate. In addition, babies are also exposed to phthalates by chewing on toys that contain Phthalates.^[7,6]

2. Metabolism

The metabolism of the human body is quick due to the short biological half-life of phthalates, estimated at 12 hours^[8] phthalates are metabolized through several steps. First, hydrolyzation occurs after phthalates enter the cell.

Then, the phthalates conjugate to form the hydrophilic glucuronide conjugate, which happens because of the action of the enzyme uridine 5'-diphosphoglucuronyl transferase. Phthalates in the body can have different toxicological properties depending on their chemical characteristics. For instance, short-branched phthalates will be hydrolysed to monoester compounds, which are subsequently expelled through urine.^[9]

For instance, DEHP can break down through hydrolysis to produce various types of monoesters including mono(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (MEHP), mono(2-ethyl-5-hydroxyhexyl) phthalate, mono(2-ethyl-5-oxohexyl) phthalate, mono(2-ethyl-5-carboxypentyl) phthalate (MECPP), mono(2-carboxymethylhexyl) phthalate (MCMHP), among others. DEHP metabolites may be

present in serum as well. According to research done on animals.^[10]

Figure 1.1: The Hidden Health Risks of Phthalates.

3. Toxicity

Phthalates have been found to have a low level of acute toxicity in the animal models such as rats, in which the LD50 value is estimated to be between 1-30 g/kg body weight. The major targeted organs which get toxic effect from phthalates include the liver, kidneys, thyroid, and testicles. There is extensive proof of toxicity related to reproductive development in both animals and humans. Toxicity testing of Dibutyl phthalate on pregnant mouse has cleared that doses of 100 mg/kg body weight are detrimental to fetus development.^[11] The impact of phthalates on human health is modifications in gene expression to physiological alterations.

There is evidence to show that exposure to high molecular weight phthalates results in methylation of imprinting genes, which may affect hormone action and protein secretion.^[12] Di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate exposure may lead to insulin resistance, increased systolic blood pressure, and problems with the reproductive system such as premature menopause, underweight births, spontaneous abortion, and pre-term deliveries.^[4] The 2003–2004 NHANES found that exposure was common across the United States. Females had higher concentrations than males, which could have been due to high usage of consumer goods such as soap and cosmetics.^[13]

4. Restrictions on Phthalate

Japan - Diisononyl Phthalate and Di(2-ethylhexyl) Phthalate are completely banned plastic food handling gloves.^[14] Europe - Diisononyl Phthalate and Diisononyl Phthalate are banned in children skin care products.^[15] The United States - Children's toys and childcare articles, along with any children's products that can be placed in the mouth of a child, and childcare articles containing over 0.1 percent of Diisononyl phthalate, are banned. In addition to this, children's plastic products containing more than 1 percent of DEHP are also banned.^[16]

Recommendation

Restrict appropriately high-risk products as necessary. In some countries, there have been restrictions put in place on certain products involving the use of Dibutyl phthalate, Benzyl butyl phthalate, Diisononyl phthalate. Such restrictions would help reduce the level of phthalate exposure. When similar restrictions are put in place by other nations where no such restrictions exist, the level of exposure will be further reduced. Such high-risk products include those that may involve contact with infants, toddlers, and adolescents through ingestion or sucking. Pregnant and lactating mothers are more susceptible to such risks and require higher restrictions when it comes to such products.

Phthalate alternative (PA) with less toxicity and leaking tendencies should be considered, especially in healthcare environments. This is because Di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate leaks from materials used, making its restriction a good idea.^[17]

The alternative softeners are citrates, benzoates, trimellitates, and adipates, with much lower toxic levels than Di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (Ruzickova, et al., 2004). Where practicable, using glass containers instead of plastic packaging, avoiding heating food in plastic containers, avoiding using fragrance that may contain phthalates, and reading the label of PCPs can easily reduce the exposure to phthalates in daily life.^[17]

CONCLUSION

The chemicals called phthalates, as well as other semi-volatile organic compounds, work as endocrine disruptors that have dangers for reproduction, neurology, and development by different pathways of exposure. Children have higher exposure levels and are more vulnerable to phthalates. Nowadays, several phthalates are prohibited or restricted in many countries. Plastics makers and distributors should be aware of plastic laws to meet national and international requirements. As of now, data on occupational exposure to phthalates is scarce.

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